

Tooth Coloured CAD/CAM PMMA Crown In A Primary Molar : A 10 Months Follow-Up

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Abstract

Preformed crowns are part of the armamentarium in Pediatric dentistry. In recent years, aesthetic alternatives to preformed metal crowns such as pre-veneered, zirconia and PMMA crowns have been developed. This paper describes the restoration of a pulpally treated primary molar with a preformed CAD/CAM PMMA crown in a 9-year-old boy over a 10 month follow-up period. At the end of the observation period the retentivity of the PMMA crown, the gingival response and the wear on the opposing tooth were considered on the basis of a predefined criteria. It was concluded that the Pediatric CAD/CAM assisted PMMA crown allowed sustainable functional restoration while restoring natural appearance of the tooth.

Key Words : CAD/CAM, PMMA crown, Aesthetics, Primary Molar

Introduction

Stainless steel crowns have been the gold standard in restoring pulpally treated primary molars^[1] but owing to the metallic appearance, higher aesthetic zirconia crowns with superior clinical performance have emerged as a better treatment option. However, their usage is limited due to inadequate documentation of the benefits of zirconia crowns and wear of opposing tooth due to higher compressive strength of the material.^[2]

Therefore, a material is required which can fulfil the need of full coverage and aesthetics while being more economical than zirconia. In recent years, digital dentistry has rapidly developed, especially computer-aided design and manufacturing (CAD/CAM) with different types of biocompatible restorative materials.^[2] Preformed CAD/CAM crowns formulated from PMMA (Poly-methyl methacrylate) blanks are an option for extra coronal restorations in primary dentition. The unique properties of these crowns, such as low density, high aesthetics, cost-effectiveness, ease of manipulation, tailorable physical and mechanical properties,^[3] good wear resistance, high polishability, color stability, good marginal fit with optimal strength,^[4] and biocompatibility with the oral tissues^[4] make them suitable and

popular biomaterial in Pediatric dentistry.

Case Presentation

A 9-year-old boy accompanied by his parents came to the Department of Pedodontics & Preventive Dentistry with a chief complaint of pain in lower left back tooth region. Radiographic examination revealed a carious lesion involving pulp in-relation-to 74. Treatment included pulpectomy with full-coverage crown. Parents were explained about the treatment options and a written consent was taken before the procedure. As parents were highly concerned with the aesthetic appearance and having financial constraints at the same time, it was decided to use our in-house CAD/CAM laboratory for preparing PMMA crown for a pulpectomy treated tooth.

An appropriate crown size was selected prior to the tooth preparation by measuring the mesiodistal dimension.(Figure-1) In this case, we used a standard crown size of 4 (3M ESPE) as reference.

Occlusal preparation of 1.5-2 mm was done using the marginal ridge of the adjacent tooth as a reference point.

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Proximal preparation of 0.5–1.25mm around the circumference, following the natural contour of the original tooth was done. Subgingival preparation of approximately 1–1.5mm below the CEJ, avoiding damage to the gingival tissues was done. All sharp line and point angles were rounded off.

Crown trial was done clinically before cementation owing to the inflexible nature of the crowns. A proper marginal fit of the crown was achieved by reducing the bucco-lingual thickness of the margins. An advantage of the fact that PMMA can be trimmed & polished, both the internal and external surfaces of the crown were adjusted chairside.

The tooth and crown were cleaned of all the blood and saliva residues prior to cementation. A self-adhesive resin cement (Densplysironacalibra universal) was used for luting. (Figure-2:a,b) A monthly check-up appointment was scheduled for the patient, however he came after 10 months as he failed to report to the department earlier.

At the end of 10-months, crown was evaluated based on 3 parameters. Retention was clinically evaluated by visual assessment, according to the USPHS, alpha criteria rating system.^[5] Gingival response was checked by Loe and Silness index (1967)^[6]. Occlusal wear on the opposing tooth was assessed by Smith and Knight Tooth Wear Index.^[7] In this case the PMMA crown was performing well on all the criteria with a score alpha in USPHS, alpha criteria rating system, score 0 in both Loe and Silness index and Smith and Knight Tooth Wear Index.

Discussion

In light of this clinical scenario, an alternate treatment option for restoring pulpally-treated primary molar needing full-coverage crown within acceptable cost range and aesthetic appearance has been highlighted. Several researchers have investigated the use of CAD/CAM technologies for the fabrication of PMMA dental prostheses using rapid prototyping and milling techniques^[3] which shows superiority in terms of several properties, including hardness, flexural strength, impact strength and durability.^[3] Good clinical retention and durability of the pre-formed milled PMMA crown were one of the positive observation of this case. The aesthetic appearance was natural and clinically acceptable. The main advantage of CAD/CAM Pre-fabricated PMMA crown as described by Pascutti et al is it's ease in fabrication, along with less chairside time consumption and cost-effectiveness.^[8] Resistance to occlusal wear is an important consideration for the clinical success of oral prosthetic restorations. The wear of the restorative material should match with that of natural enamel.^[9] In our case, wear patterns on the PMMA crown were seen on occlusal surface along with chipping on distolingual margin during the 10-month follow-up period. (Figure-3) At the same time no accelerated occlusal wear was seen on opposing intact natural tooth.(Figure-4) This finding is consistent with that of Claudia Florina Andreescu who mentioned that CAD/CAM fabricated milled crowns possess good fracture resistance as they have almost zero porosity and high

homogeneity.^[8] Two disadvantages perceived preoperatively were higher thickness of PMMA crown than preformed metal crown and a need for subgingival preparation wherever necessary. These aspects could influence the gingival response and health. However, in this case no gingival inflammation was noted around the crown as the patient maintained good oral hygiene through out the follow-up period. This finding is in tune with the fact that when the oral hygiene is maintained properly, there is no noticeable gingival inflammation.^[10] Further advantage of this material is enhanced hydrophobicity and specific surface properties^[3] resulting in inhibition of plaque accumulation,^[4] leading to good gingival response. Along the same line, Atay et al.^[4] also pointed out that new generations of CAD/CAM milled PMMA can safely be used in clinical conditions. As a result, PMMA has emerged as a suitable material for prefabricated crowns to be used in pediatric patients. However, an evaluation of the long-term success of these crowns is definitely needed, with more clinical cases in different scenarios.

Conclusion

In this case, Preformed crown prepared with PMMA blank using in house CAD/CAM milling procedure has shown good performance over a 10-month follow-up period.

References

1. Kindelan SA, Day P, Nichol R, Willmott N, Fayle SA; British Society of Paediatric Dentistry. UK National Clinical Guidelines in Paediatric Dentistry: stainless steel preformed crowns for primary molars. *Int J Paediatr Dent* 2008;18(1):20–28.
2. Mohammed Nour Al-Halabi, Nada Bshara, Jihad Abou Nassar, John C. Comisi, Charline K. Rizk. Clinical Performance of Two Types of Primary Molar Indirect Crowns Fabricated by 3D Printer and CAD/CAM for Rehabilitation of Large Carious Primary. *Molar.Eur J Dent.* 2021 Jul; 15(3):463–468.
3. Zafar MS. Prosthodontic Applications of Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA): An Update. *Polymers.* 2020; 12(10):2299.
4. Pituru SM, Greabu M, Totan A, Imre M, Pantea M, Spinu T, et al. A Review on the Biocompatibility of PMMA-Based Dental Materials for Interim Prosthetic Restorations with a Glimpse into their Modern Manufacturing Techniques. *Materials (Basel).* 2020 Jun 28; 13(13):2894.
5. Ryge G. Clinical criteria. *Int Dent J.* 1980;30:34–58.
6. Löe H. The Gingival Index, the Plaque Index and the Retention Index Systems. *J Periodontol.* 1967 Nov-Dec;38(6):610-616.
7. Smith BG, Knight JK. An index for measuring the wear of teeth. *Br Dent J* 1984;156:435–438.

8. BodhisattaMukherjeea, Upasana Panda B, Gautam Naskarc, Monika Samald, Gopal Krishna Choudhury E. A comparative analysis of wear resistance, surface hardness and fracture resistance of interim restoration fabricated by cad/cam and conventional method. Eur. Chem. Bull. 2023,12(6):856–864.
9. Meghana Reddy J, Ashok V, Kiran Kumar and Dhanraj Ganapathy. Comparative Evaluation of Wear Resistance Among Cad-Cam and Resin Interim Restoration - an in Vitro Study. Bioscience Biotechnology Research Communication 2020; 13 (8):224-228.
10. Lopez Cazaux S, Hyon I, Prud'homme T, et al. Twenty-nine-month follow-up of a paediatric zirconia dental crown. BMJ Case Rep 2017.

Figure-1 Intraoral pre-operative clinical photo

Figure-2 : a Intra-oral view immediately after PMMA crown cemented

Figure-2 : b Occlusal relation after cementation

Figure-3 Clinical photo at 10 month follow-up

Figure-4 Intact opposing tooth at 10 month follow-up